

IMPROVING THE TEACHING OF PHYSICS AND ASTRONOMY BASED ON NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND THE STEAM EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This study discusses the improvement of teaching physics and astronomy, particularly in general education schools. It provides insights into enhancing the teaching process using modern pedagogical technologies and highlights the advantages of the STEAM education system. The study emphasizes the importance of utilizing contemporary educational technologies to improve the quality of physics and astronomy education.*

Keywords: *communication, principle, individual, PISA, STEAM.*

Introduction.

Physics is a science that studies the phenomena and events occurring in our surroundings, as well as the laws governing them. A deep understanding of all natural phenomena and the identification of their fundamental principles primarily belong to the fields of physics and astronomy. Among all natural sciences, physics and astronomy hold an unparalleled place.

In today's rapidly developing world of science and technology, it is essential to organize the teaching of natural sciences, particularly physics and astronomy, in accordance with modern educational standards. Therefore, integrating contemporary pedagogical and information communication technologies into the teaching process and aligning theoretical knowledge with practical applications should form the foundation of physics and astronomy education. Only through this approach can the desired educational goals be achieved.

The didactic principles applied in teaching include scientific rigor, educational value, systematization, consciousness, consistency, visualization, reinforcement, and others. These principles form the didactic foundation of teaching physics and astronomy, and it is important that both teachers and students become well acquainted with them. For instance, if we consider the principle of visualization, demonstrating phenomena, processes, and related laws in a visual manner during lessons significantly enhances students' comprehension of the subject matter.

In today's rapidly changing world, the creation of an innovative educational environment that meets international standards is an essential requirement. To ensure effective teaching of physics and astronomy in general education schools, each topic should be explained in connection with real-world applications, using relevant demonstrations, innovative methods, and technical tools. Such an approach is expected to yield positive learning outcomes.

Another crucial factor in education that every teacher should always consider is that each student is unique, with distinct characteristics. Therefore, an individualized approach should be adopted, taking into account each student's level of understanding, perception, and interest in the subject.

Methodology.

For students with lower academic performance and weaker memory retention, a step-by-step approach is essential. For example, if a student is asked to find z in the equation $x = y/z$, it is more effective to first guide them through simpler cases.

By demonstrating:

- $3 = 6/2$, then solving for 2 , leading to $2 = 6/3$,
- Or solving for 6 as $6 = 2 \times 3$,

The student will grasp the logical structure more easily. Once they are comfortable with these basic transformations, they will be able to confidently determine z and y in the general formula:

- $z = y/x$
- $y = x \times z$

This gradual method ensures a deeper understanding and a stronger foundation for solving algebraic equations.

Alternatively, to further enhance students' interest in the subject, it is effective to demonstrate various simple examples in a visual and practical manner. For instance, while teaching the topic "Determining the Acceleration of Free Fall," using a small hammer and a feather as an example would be an appropriate and engaging approach.

This is because they can be used not only on Earth's surface (such as in the famous Pisa Tower experiment) but also in other environments to demonstrate the principles of free fall.

Piza minorasi

but also on the Moon, which is Earth's only natural satellite, located 384,400 km away from us.

Oy sirtida sayohat

(This experiment was conducted on the Moon, demonstrating that despite having different masses, the hammer and the feather fall at the same rate from a given height. The results confirmed that in the absence of air resistance, the acceleration due to gravity is independent of mass.)

To make physics and astronomy lessons more engaging, teachers can encourage students to participate in discussions and debates by presenting thought-provoking problems. For example:

- Why does a person inside a moving car, when the car suddenly brakes, hit the back of their seat forcefully?
- Why does a 1 kg stone sink in water, while a much larger wooden plank remains afloat?

Results and discussion.

Explaining such questions through scientific principles makes the learning process more interesting and stimulates students' curiosity and critical thinking.

In this context, the STEAM education system holds a significant place in modern education and continues to expand globally.

This system integrates various fields such as science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics into a unified approach to education. The core idea behind STEAM is that practical application is just as important as theoretical knowledge. In a STEAM-based learning environment, acquired knowledge is immediately applied in practice. This system helps students develop knowledge, determination, creativity, and teamwork skills, preparing them for real-world problem-solving and innovation.

In accordance with the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Additional Measures to Improve the Management System of Public Education” (PF-5538) and the implementation of the Presidential Resolution No. PP-3931 (September 5, 2018), a comprehensive Action Plan for 2018–2021 was adopted to enhance the public education system. Section II, Clause 11 of this program outlines the need for modernizing state education standards and curricula for general secondary education while gradually implementing STEAM methodologies in practice.

At the core of STEAM education lies scientific inquiry and artistic exploration. In today’s era of technological revolution, new innovations are constantly being developed and introduced into practice, leading to the continuous evolution of education in both content and approach. When interactive teaching methods are used, teacher-student interaction becomes more dynamic, fostering collaboration and ensuring effective knowledge acquisition. By integrating various

modern pedagogical technologies, students are encouraged not only to conduct independent research but also to analyze their knowledge and draw conclusions.

During lessons, both teachers and students strive toward a common goal, and selecting the appropriate teaching method is crucial in maintaining interest in the subject. For natural sciences, particularly physics and astronomy, connecting theoretical concepts with real-world phenomena makes learning more engaging.

For example, when teaching the topic of “Speed of Light,” students can be introduced to the concept through an example: The nearest star to us, the Sun, is about 150 million km away, and its light travels at 300,000 km/s, reaching Earth in approximately 8 minutes. A challenging question can then be posed: *The second closest star to Earth, Proxima Centauri, emits light that takes 4 years to reach Earth. Given the speed of light, what is the distance between Earth and Proxima Centauri?*

To solve this problem, students must engage in critical thinking and mathematical calculations, determining: The number of seconds in a minute, minutes in an hour, hours in a day, and days in a year, and ultimately computing the distance using the speed-time-distance formula.

Conclusion.

In summary, improving the teaching of physics and astronomy in general education schools requires the integration of modern pedagogical technologies and the STEAM education system. This innovative approach forms the foundation for providing students with comprehensive and high-quality knowledge, preparing them for scientific and technological advancements in the modern world.

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